

Rac-7d

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-153-2-RAC-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	37	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 3 153 2 rac
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	266.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 266.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	7/27/2022 8:06:23 PM CST		
Date Processed:	7/27/2022 10:50:52 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	11.518	1350388	50.08	71219
2	12.756	1346258	49.92	64075

Asy-7d

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-153-2-asy-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	93	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 3 153 2 asy
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	266.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 266.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	7/27/2022 10:32:31 PM CST		
Date Processed:	7/27/2022 10:49:18 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	11.483	452637	4.13	24649
2	12.715	10499150	95.87	492455